

MultiXscale

Coupling ESPReso with waLBerla

MultiXscale Deliverable 3.3
Deliverable Type: Other
Delivered in June, 2025

MultiXscale
EuroHPC Centre of Excellence for
Multiscale Modelling

Co-funded by
the European Union

Acknowledgement

Funded by the European Union. This work has received funding from the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 101093169.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project and Deliverable Information

Project Title Project Ref. Project Website EuroHPC Project Officer	MultiXscale: EuroHPC Centre of Excellence for Multiscale Modelling Grant Agreement 101093169 https://www.multixscale.eu Matteo Mascagni
Deliverable ID Deliverable Nature Dissemination Level Contractual Date of Delivery Actual Date of Delivery	D3.3 Other Public Project Month 30 (30 th June, 2025) 27 th June, 2025
Description of Deliverable	Software release of ESPResSo with waLBerla support for Lattice-Boltzmann.

Document Control Information

Document	Title:	Coupling ESPResSo with waLBerla
	ID:	D3.3
	Version:	As of June, 2025
	Status:	Accepted by Steering Committee
	Available at:	https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables
	Document history:	Internal Project Management Link
Review	Review Status:	Reviewed
Authorship	Written by:	Rudolf Weeber (USTUTT)
	Contributors:	Jean-Noël Grad (USTUTT)
	Reviewed by:	Alan Ó Cais (UB)
	Approved by:	Alan Ó Cais (UB)

Document Keywords

Keywords:	MultiXscale, HPC
-----------	------------------

27th June, 2025

Disclaimer: This deliverable has been prepared by the responsible Work Package of the Project in accordance with the Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement. It solely reflects the opinion of the parties to such agreements on a collective basis in the context of the Project and to the extent foreseen in such agreements.

Copyright notices: This deliverable was co-ordinated by Rudolf Weeber¹ (USTUTT) on behalf of the MultiXscale consortium with contributions from Jean-Noël Grad (USTUTT). This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. To view a copy of this license, visit:

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>

¹weeber@icp.uni-stuttgart.de

Contents

Executive Summary	1
1 Introduction	2
1.1 Making release candidates of ESPResSo available via dev.eessi.io	2
1.2 Target audience	2
1.3 Deliverable outline	3
1.4 Partner contributions	3
2 Software Architecture	4
3 Coupling molecular dynamics to lattice-Boltzmann hydrodynamics	5
4 Coupling of a diffusion-advection-reaction solver to lattice-Boltzmann	6
5 Parallel I/O	7
6 Conclusion and perspectives	9
Acknowledgements	10
References	10

List of Figures

1 Visualisation of fluid flow around solid objects	3
2 Workflow for the code generation.	4
3 Parallel efficiency of multi-GPU lattice-Boltzmann (weak scaling)	5
4 Parallel write performance of HDF5/MPI-IO on BeeGFS (strong scaling)	7
5 Serial write performance of HDF5/MPI-IO on ext4 (strong scaling)	8
6 Parallel write performance of VTK on BeeGFS (strong scaling)	8

List of Listings

1 Using ESPResSo via the dev.eessi.io stack	2
2 Part of the API provided by the WalberlaBridge library	4

Executive Summary

This companion document to Deliverable 3.3 describes how the simulation package ESPResSo is coupled to waLBerla. By way of combining these packages, we couple lattice-Boltzmann hydrodynamics to molecular dynamics and to a diffusion-advection-reaction solver, respectively. A particular focus is making waLBerla's multi-GPU capabilities accessible to ESPResSo to off-load hydrodynamics calculations. These improvements will greatly benefit simulations on the meso scale, where particle-solvent interactions play a critical role in the dynamics of the modelled system. The main sections of this report will focus on:

- the technical architecture of the ESPResSo-waLBerla-coupling (Section 2),
- molecular dynamics of particles interacting with hydrodynamic fields (Section 4),
- coupling of the lattice-Boltzmann hydrodynamics solver with a diffusion-advection-reaction solver for modelling electrokinetics (Section 3),
- scalable parallel Input/Output (I/O) for data exchange between different simulation software (Section 5).

1 Introduction

For simulations in soft matter science and process engineering on the mesoscale, it is often not sufficient to model only particles. On these scales, a solvent such as water is nearly always present. Therefore, whenever the dynamics of a system are explored, one has to couple molecular dynamics to a hydrodynamics solver. The lattice-Boltzmann method [1] is particularly well suited to this task: it provides many possibilities in terms of boundary conditions and particle coupling (Fig. 1), can include thermal fluctuations which are crucial at the meso scale, and can be parallelized well, particularly on GPUs.

Tailored for coarse-grained models on the meso scale, Extensible Simulation Package for Research on Soft Matter Systems (ESPResSo) 4.2 [2] provides molecular dynamics in combination with two custom lattice-Boltzmann implementations, one for the CPU and one for the GPU. These have several limitations, in particular, the GPU implementation in ESPResSo 4.2 is limited to a single GPU. This inherently limits scalability and system size.

Within the MultiXscale CoE, we are replacing ESPResSo's custom lattice-Boltzmann and electrokinetics implementations with ones backed by the `waLBerla` [3] framework. This framework provides highly scalable solvers for stencil methods, such as lattice-Boltzmann. Moreover, its companion packages, `PyStencils` [4] and `LbmPy` [5], enable automated code generation, making it much easier to modify and enhance the lattice-based methods.

The coupling to ESPResSo was developed in collaboration with the `waLBerla` team. Aside from providing the coupling to ESPResSo, we also occasionally contributed back to `waLBerla`, e.g., with respect to the thermalised lattice-Boltzmann method and static code analysis.

1.1 Making release candidates of ESPResSo available via `dev.eessi.io`

The ESPResSo release candidate with `waLBerla` coupling was released on the European Environment for Scientific Software Installations (EESSI) [6] in collaboration with the University of Barcelona, the University of Groningen, and Ghent University, and can be loaded on all clusters where EESSI is available natively². The repository that controls the deployment to `dev.eessi.io` is the [ESPResSo repository under the MultiXscale GitHub organisation](#). For details on how the `dev.eessi.io` repository works please refer to the [EESSI documentation for dev.eessi.io](#).

Listing 1 shows the steps necessary to access the release candidate version of ESPResSo (with an example given for a specific commit of ESPResSo but available versions will change over time). The release candidates can (and are) being used by external projects in their own (EESSI-supported) continuous integration (CI) workflows. For an example of this, see the [pyMBE-dev/pyMBE#133](#) pull request in the Python-based Molecule Builder for ESPResSo (pyMBE) [7] project that enabled the use of ESPResSo from the `dev.eessi.io` repository in their CI pipeline.

```

1 source /cvmfs/software.eessi.io/versions/2023.06/init/lmod/bash
2 module use /cvmfs/dev.eessi.io/espresso/versions/${EESSI_VERSION}/software/linux/${EESSI_SOFTWARE_SUBDIR}/modules/all
3 # Available versions use a specific commit/toolchain and may change over time
4 module load ESPResSo/8aa60cecd10ab62042c567552f347374f36-foss-2023b

```

Listing 1: Using ESPResSo via the `dev.eessi.io` stack.

In this companion document to Deliverable 3.3 (which is the software release itself), we provide technical details of the implementation and the molecular dynamics to lattice-Boltzmann and electrokinetics to lattice-Boltzmann couplings, respectively.

1.2 Target audience

This deliverable is aimed at (but not limited) to:

- people employing molecular dynamics (MD) simulations,
- people using ESPResSo MD simulation code,
- people interested in the architecture and capabilities of ESPResSo,
- people interested in testing the specific release of ESPResSo covered by this document,
- people interested in coupling Widely Applicable Lattice Boltzmann solver from ERLAnge (waLBerla) to their own application.

²<https://www.eessi.io/docs/systems/>

Figure 1: Visualisation of settling dynamics. Nanoparticles (grey spheres) are suspended in a fluid and are subject to gravity. During their fall, friction with the fluid causes the formation of a fluid flow (magenta arrows) that brings the nanoparticles together into a droplet, which eventually disperses into a circular pattern upon contact with the bottom wall of the container. Rendered with ZnVis [8]. Image credits: Paul Hohenberger.

1.3 Deliverable outline

The specific deliverable is of type *Other*, and is a specific release of the ESPResSo package. The release of the software has been made via EESSI on the `dev.eessi.io` CernVM-FS repository. The current document is a supporting document for that release.

Section 2 covers the software architecture of the coupling between ESPResSo and waLBerla. Section 3 describes the coupling of MD to lattice-Boltzmann (LB) hydrodynamics, and shows the weak-scaling efficiency of this coupling. Section 4 describes the electrokinetics coupling to waLBerla. Section 5 describes the new parallel I/O implementation for ESPResSo.

1.4 Partner contributions

USTUTT contributed as planned to the work in this deliverable.

2 Software Architecture

On a technical level, ESPResSo uses waLBerla as a library. When building ESPResSo, waLBerla is obtained via CMake's FetchContent mechanism and built along with ESPResSo. The solvers provided by waLBerla are then controlled, as for previous versions of ESPResSo, via ESPResSo's Python interface. I.e., for end users, the switch to waLBerla is largely transparent. To keep the interface to ESPResSo as narrow as possible, and to allow for the re-use of the coupling code in other software, the code implementing the coupling to waLBerla is separated into a WalberlaBridge component. This is basically a separate library which handles the details of using waLBerla but has only minimal dependencies on ESPResSo. The re-use of the coupling component with LAMMPS is currently being explored by our partners at NIC. Part of the application programming interface (API) is reproduced in Listing 2.

Both the lattice-Boltzmann and electrokinetics solvers heavily rely on waLBerla's code generation capabilities, i.e., the mathematical structure and equations for the methods are defined in terms of symbolic math. For basic lattice-Boltzmann components like streaming the collision operator, these definitions are provided in LbmPy, for other aspects, such as Lees-Edwards boundary conditions, these are provided by ESPResSo. These definitions are then translated to efficient C++ or CUDA kernels by PyStencils, making use of vectorisation where possible. As a result, kernels can be generated for different hardware from the same sources. The full workflow of the code generation is depicted in Fig. 2. As the code generation has additional dependencies, we chose to ship pre-generated C++ and CUDA source files for the kernels with ESPResSo for both, single and double precision, as well as with and without AVX2 vectorisation. However, should users wish to customize the implementation and/or support other hardware features, the generation pipeline is provided as part of the ESPResSo source tree.

Figure 2: Workflow for the code generation.

```

1 /** @brief Interface of a lattice-based fluid model. */
2 class LBWalberlaBase : public LatticeModel {
3 public:
4 /** @brief Integrate LB for one time step. */
5 virtual void integrate() = 0;
6
7 /** @brief Perform a full ghost communication. */
8 virtual void ghost_communication() = 0;
9
10 /** @brief Get interpolated velocities at a position. */
11 virtual std::optional<Utils::Vector3d>
12 get_velocity_at_pos(Utils::Vector3d const &position,
13                    bool consider_points_in_halo = false) const = 0;
14
15 /** @brief Interpolate a force to the stored forces to be applied on nodes in the next time step. */
16 virtual bool add_force_at_pos(Utils::Vector3d const &position,
17                               Utils::Vector3d const &force) = 0;
18
19 /** @brief Get node velocity. */
20 virtual std::optional<Utils::Vector3d>
21 get_node_velocity(Utils::Vector3i const &node,
22                  bool consider_ghosts = false) const = 0;
23
24 /** @brief Set node velocity. */
25 virtual bool set_node_velocity(Utils::Vector3i const &node,
26                               Utils::Vector3d const &velocity) = 0;
27
28 // [...]
29 };
  
```

Listing 2: Part of the API provided by the WalberlaBridge library. It offers the capabilities needed to couple a MD simulation but hides the details of using waLBerla. This allows for the use of the library with other MD codes than ESPResSo in the future.

3 Coupling molecular dynamics to lattice-Boltzmann hydrodynamics

We implement two coupling schemes, namely momentum-exchange coupling [9] and inertialess tracers [10]. The former is typically used to couple ions, colloidal particles, and polymers, while the latter is used in conjunction with the immersed boundary method for coupling deformable objects such as red blood cells.

For the momentum exchange method, the coupling consists of the following steps:

1. Obtain fluid velocity at the particle positions by interpolation from the closest lattice-Boltzmann grid points.
2. Calculate coupling force based on the velocity difference between fluid and particle.
3. Apply opposing coupling forces to particles and fluid. For the fluid, the force is back-interpolated onto the closest LB grid points surrounding the particles.

When using the inertialess tracers, the equation of motion of the particles is not integrated. Instead, they are propagated based on the fluid velocity at the particle position. Forces on the inertialess tracers, e.g., from the elasticity of a red blood cell, are applied directly to the fluid. In summary, for both coupling schemes, we need to obtain interpolated fluid velocities at the particle positions and apply forces to the fluid at the particle positions, by back-interpolation.

When running lattice-Boltzmann on a GPU, the interpolation is handled on the GPU. I.e., there are two kernel calls for the coupling, the first to obtain interpolated fluid velocities, the second to apply forces to the fluid. The corresponding data transfer consists of 3 floating point values per particle for the former and 6 for the latter. This results in typical transfer volumes between 1 and 10 MB. The actual flow field, approximately 50 floating point values per lattice-Boltzmann grid point, is never communicated to the CPU unless requested by the user for I/O. The lattice-Boltzmann solver in *ESPResSo* can be run in both double and single precision. As LB is limited by memory bandwidth on GPUs, the latter performs significantly better and is often sufficient when the simulation includes Brownian motion. On the HPC Vega supercomputer, the parallel efficiency is 75% when more than one compute node is allocated (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Weak scaling efficiency of a multi-GPU unthermalised lattice-Boltzmann fluid simulation with particle coupling on HPC Vega (two 64-core AMD EPYC Rome 7H12 CPUs and four NVIDIA A100 GPUs per node). The simulated system contains 10k particles and approx. 4 million cells per GPU on a 158x158x158 grid for a volume fraction of 1%.

4 Coupling of a diffusion-advection-reaction solver to lattice-Boltzmann

For modelling charged solutes in a flow, ESPResSo provides a finite volume-based solver for diffusion-advection-reaction equations combined with electrostatics, which is coupled to the lattice-Boltzmann solver. The approach relies on a continuity equation for the solute density, which describes the change of solute concentration in a region at a given point in time by the solute fluxes in and out of that region [11, 12]. The fluxes occur due to:

- Fickian diffusion, i.e., flux from a region with high solute concentration to one with a lower concentration
- Electrostatic forces. In addition to any external electric fields, charged solutes move according to an electrostatic potential which they themselves create
- Advection, i.e., the solutes are carried along by an underlying flow of the solvent

Lastly, when solutes move due to diffusion and electrostatic forces, they will also drag along the solvent.

In technical terms, electrokinetics is implemented as follows. The solute concentration is solved via a finite-volume based solver via `waLBerla`. Like with lattice-Boltzmann, this replaces a previous custom implementation in ESPResSo 4.2 and relies on automated code generation. This solver co-runs with lattice-Boltzmann, sharing the infrastructure for the lattice and the fields. In this way, the finite volume solver can directly access the flow velocity and add forces to the fluid without data being copied.

The simulation consists of the following steps, starting from an initial solute concentration and fluid flow field:

1. Calculate charge distribution based on the concentration of solute species (`waLBerla` kernel).
2. Calculate electrostatic potential due to the solutes using an FFT-based solver for the Poisson equation.
3. Calculate solute fluxes due to solute diffusion and electrostatics (`waLBerla` kernel).
4. Calculate advective solute fluxes based on the flow velocity from lattice-Boltzmann (`waLBerla` kernel).
5. Apply forces to lattice-Boltzmann based on solute fluxes dragging along the fluid (`waLBerla` kernel).
6. Integrate the diffusion-advection-reaction solver and lattice-Boltzmann by one time step (`waLBerla` kernels).

At this point, the electrokinetics solver is available for the CPU, but a GPU implementation is in preparation. As the `waLBerla` kernels used in the solver are all based on `waLBerla`'s automated code generation capabilities, CUDA kernels can be generated from the same source files. This will not involve large code changes. Only the Poisson solver, handled by the `PFFT` library on the CPU, will need to be replaced by a GPU-capable solver, e.g., based on `CuFFT` or `heFFTe`.

5 Parallel I/O

Aside from the couplings built directly into ESPResSo, couplings are often simply realized by using the output of one simulation software as input to another one. To this end, we have considerably improved the scalability of parallel output in ESPResSo. Particle data can be stored to disk in binary format via MPI Input/Output (MPI-IO) [13] or in a portable format via Hierarchical Data Format version 5 (HDF5) [14]. The former is typically used to create hardware-specific checkpoints to help restart simulations that have been interrupted, while the latter is designed for data sharing. HDF5 is a portable and standardized file format that also supports metadata, which ESPResSo leverages to store SI units according to the H5MD [15] specification. It is provided to allow for interoperability with the other codes involved in the CoE, and can be used with LAMMPS, VMD (visualisation), and VOTCA (systematic coarse-graining). Grid-based data such as fluid velocity fields, fluid pressure tensor fields, or electrokinetic species concentrations, are written to disk using portable VTK [16] file formats, more specifically multi-piece uniform grids XML files. These files can be natively read by the ParaView software [17] and the vtk Python package.

The original HDF5 backend implemented in ESPResSo had numerous bottlenecks that made it unsuitable for parallel simulations. It also relied on unmaintained third-party codes that didn't support modern compiler toolchains available on EuroHPC-JU systems and EESSI. For these reasons, a new implementation based on the HighFive [18] library was introduced as a replacement. The new HDF5 backend has a much better performance profile compared to the MPI-IO backend on a BeeGFS [19] parallel file system (Figure 4), and maintains a near-constant parallel write rate. The new HDF5 backend is also several orders of magnitude faster than the original backend on the ext4 [20] serial file system (Figure 5); that benchmark was conducted on a desktop workstation by necessity, since the original HDF5 backend doesn't compile on clusters anymore.

The original VTK backend implemented in ESPResSo used the serial code and was unsuitable for parallel simulations. The new VTK backend is a built-in functionality of waLBerla and writes multi-piece uniform grids in XML format. Two parallel write strategies are available: MPI-IO, which writes data to a single file in parallel at the cost of a small communication overhead to compute file offsets, and one-file-per-process (OFPP), where each MPI rank writes to its own file to avoid communication. The new VTK backend shows excellent parallel performance on a BeeGFS [19] parallel file system (Figure 6), especially the OFPP strategy whose bandwidth is monotonously increasing.

Figure 4: Strong scaling performance of particle-based writers on a BeeGFS file system (4700 MB/s parallel write rate) on the Ant cluster (two 32-core AMD EPYC 9374F CPUs per node). The simulated system contains 260k particles.

Figure 5: Strong scaling performance of particle-based writers on an ext4 file system (2800 MB/s serial write rate) on a desktop workstation equipped with a 16-core AMD Ryzen 9 CPU. The simulated system contains 16k particles.

Figure 6: Strong scaling performance of grid-based writers on a BeeGFS file system (4700 MB/s parallel write rate) on the Ant cluster (two 32-core AMD EPYC 9374F CPUs per node). The simulated system contains 128x128x256 cells (4.2 million cells) and writes the fluid velocity field (3 floating-point values per cell).

6 Conclusion and perspectives

In conclusion, we have prepared a version of ESPResSo in which lattice-Boltzmann hydrodynamics and electrokinetics are provided by a coupling to waLBerla. This state-of-the-art High Performance Computing (HPC) library replaces previous custom implementations which did not scale well.

Most importantly, ESPResSo by means of waLBerla now enables multi-GPU hydrodynamics simulations with excellent scaling on HPC Vega. Similar work is currently ongoing for the diffusion-advection-reaction solver, which uses the same framework and is already available as a fully-functional CPU implementation. Moreover, both, lattice-Boltzmann and diffusion-advection solvers rely on waLBerla's automated code-generation capabilities which considerably lowers the effort for porting to a new architecture or modifying the algorithms. Two couplings are provided in ESPResSo, namely one between molecular dynamics and lattice-Boltzmann hydrodynamics to study particles in flow, and one between the diffusion-advection solver and lattice-Boltzmann hydrodynamics in order to solve electrokinetics. On a technical level, the ESPResSo-waLBerla coupling library has minimal dependencies with ESPResSo and is currently being investigated by our partners at NIC to introduce waLBerla in LAMMPS.

Aside from the couplings directly provided by ESPResSo in conjunction with waLBerla, data is often simply exchanged via files when coupling different scientific software packages. To this end, we also presents the new parallel output modules implemented in ESPResSo within MultiXscale and show measurements of their performance on a university cluster. The new version of the HDF5 and VTK writers are orders of magnitude faster than the initial codes and fully leverage parallel files systems available in supercomputers.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking for awarding access to Vega at IZUM, Slovenia, as well as funding from the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) Compute Cluster grant no. 492175459 (PI: Holm) for the Ant cluster. The authors would like to thank Alan O’Cais, Kenneth Hoste, and Pedro Santos Neves for their invaluable help in setting up ESPResSo on EESSI.

References

Acronyms used

EESSI European Environment for Scientific Software Installations
HPC High Performance Computing
MPI Message Passing Interface
LB lattice-Boltzmann
FFT fast Fourier transform
I/O Input/Output
CUDA Compute Unified Device Architecture
XML Extensible Markup Language
AVX2 Advanced Vector Extensions 2
HDF5 Hierarchical Data Format version 5
H5MD HDF5 for molecular data
MD molecular dynamics
CI continuous integration
pyMBE Python-based Molecule Builder for ESPResSo
API application programming interface
OFPP one-file-per-process
MPI-IO MPI Input/Output

Software mentioned

ESPResSo Extensible Simulation Package for Research on Soft Matter Systems
LAMMPS Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator
waLBerla Widely Applicable Lattice Boltzmann solver from ERLAngen
PFFT Parallel FFT
heFFTe Highly Efficient FFT for Exascale
VOTCA Versatile Object-oriented Toolkit for Coarse-graining Applications
VMD Visual Molecular Dynamics
VTK Visualization Toolkit

URLs referenced

Page ii

<https://www.multixscale.eu> ... <https://www.multixscale.eu>
<https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables> ... <https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables>
Internal Project Management Link ... <https://github.com/multixscale/planning/issues/151>
weeber@icp.uni-stuttgart.de ... <mailto:weeber@icp.uni-stuttgart.de>
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0> ... <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>

Page 2

<https://www.eessi.io/docs/systems/> ... <https://www.eessi.io/docs/systems/>
ESPResSo repository under the MultiXscale GitHub organisation ... <https://github.com/multixscale/dev.eessi.io-espresso>
EESSI documentation for dev.eessi.io ... https://www.eessi.io/docs/adding_software/adding_development_software/
[pyMBE-dev/pyMBE#133](https://github.com/pyMBE-dev/pyMBE#133) ... <https://github.com/pyMBE-dev/pyMBE/pull/133>

Page 10

492175459 ... <https://gepris.dfg.de/gepris/projekt/492175459?language=en>

Citations

- [1] T. Krüger, H. Kusumaatmaja, A. Kuzmin, O. Shardt, G. Silva, and E. M. Vigen, *The lattice Boltzmann method: principles and practice*, ser. Graduate texts in physics. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2017. ISBN 978-3-319-44649-3. doi:[10.1007/978-3-319-44649-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-44649-3)
- [2] R. Weeber, J.-N. Grad, D. Beyer, P. M. Blanco, P. Kreissl, A. Reinauer, I. Tischler, P. Košov, and C. Holm, “ESPResSo, a versatile open-source software package for simulating soft matter systems,” in *Comprehensive Computational Chemistry*, 1st ed., M. Yáñez and R. J. Boyd, Eds. Oxford: Elsevier, 2024, pp. 578–601. ISBN 978-0-12-823256-9. doi:[10.1016/B978-0-12-821978-2.00103-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-821978-2.00103-3)
- [3] M. Bauer, S. Eibl, C. Godenschwager, N. Kohl, M. Kuron, C. Rettinger, F. Schornbaum, C. Schwarzmeier, D. Thönes, H. Köstler, and U. Rude, “WALBERLA: A block-structured high-performance framework for multiphysics simulations,” *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, vol. 81, pp. 478–501, 2021. doi:[10.1016/j.camwa.2020.01.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.camwa.2020.01.007)
- [4] M. Bauer, J. Hötzer, D. Ernst, J. Hammer, M. Seiz, H. Hierl, J. Höning, H. Köstler, G. Wellein, B. Nestler, and U. Rude, “Code generation for massively parallel phase-field simulations,” in *Proceedings of the International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis*. New York, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2019. doi:[10.1145/3295500.3356186](https://doi.org/10.1145/3295500.3356186). ISBN 978-1-4503-6229-0
- [5] M. Bauer, H. Köstler, and U. Rude, “lbmpy: Automatic code generation for efficient parallel lattice Boltzmann methods,” *Journal of Computational Science*, vol. 49, p. 101269, 2021. doi:[10.1016/j.jocs.2020.101269](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocs.2020.101269)
- [6] B. Dröge, V. H. Rusu, K. Hoste, C. van Leeuwen, A. OCais, and T. Röblitz, “EESSI: A cross-platform ready-to-use optimised scientific software stack,” *Software: Practice and Experience*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 176–210, Jan. 2023. doi:[10.1002/spe.3075](https://doi.org/10.1002/spe.3075)
- [7] D. Beyer, P. B. Torres, S. P. Pineda, C. F. Narambuena, J.-N. Grad, P. Košov, and P. M. Blanco, “pyMBE: The Python-based molecule builder for ESPResSo,” *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, vol. 161, no. 2, Jul. 2024. doi:[10.1063/5.0216389](https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0216389)
- [8] S. Tovey, “ZnVis: A visualisation package for particle simulations, release 2.0.4,” GitHub. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/zincware/ZnVis>
- [9] B. Dünweg and A. J. C. Ladd, “Lattice Boltzmann simulations of soft matter systems,” in *Advanced computer simulation approaches for soft matter sciences III*, ser. Advances in Polymer Science, C. Holm and K. Kremer, Eds. Berlin: Springer, 2009, no. 221, pp. 89–166. ISBN 978-3-540-87706-6. doi:[10.1007/12_2008_4](https://doi.org/10.1007/12_2008_4)
- [10] T. Krüger, *Fluid-structure interaction: the immersed boundary method*. Wiesbaden: Vieweg+Teubner Verlag, 2012, pp. 37–42. ISBN 978-3-8348-2376-2. doi:[10.1007/978-3-8348-2376-2_6](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-8348-2376-2_6)
- [11] F. Capuani, I. Pagonabarraga, and D. Frenkel, “Discrete solution of the electrokinetic equations,” *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, vol. 121, pp. 973–986, 2004. doi:[10.1063/1.1760739](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1760739)
- [12] I. Tischler, F. Weik, R. Kaufmann, M. Kuron, R. Weeber, and C. Holm, “A thermalized electrokinetics model including stochastic reactions suitable for multiscale simulations of reaction–advection–diffusion systems,” *Journal of Computational Science*, vol. 63, p. 101770, Sep. 2022. doi:[10.1016/j.jocs.2022.101770](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocs.2022.101770)
- [13] P. Corbett, D. Feitelson, S. Fineberg, Y. Hsu, B. Nitzberg, J.-P. Prost, M. Snir, B. Traversat, and P. Wong, *Overview of the MPI-IO parallel I/O interface*, ser. The Kluwer International Series in Engineering and Computer Science. Boston, Massachusetts, USA: Springer US, 1996, vol. 362, pp. 127–146. ISBN 978-1-4613-1401-1. doi:[10.1007/978-1-4613-1401-1_5](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4613-1401-1_5)
- [14] The HDF Group, “Hierarchical Data Format, version 5,” GitHub. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/HDFGroup/hdf5>
- [15] P. de Buyl, P. H. Colberg, and F. Höfling, “H5MD: A structured, efficient, and portable file format for molecular data,” *Computer Physics Communications*, vol. 185, no. 6, pp. 1546–1553, 2014. doi:[10.1016/j.cpc.2014.01.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2014.01.018)
- [16] W. Schroeder, K. Martin, and B. Lorenzen, *The Visualization Toolkit. An object-oriented approach to 3D graphics*, 4th ed. New York, USA: Kitware, 2006. ISBN 9781930934191
- [17] U. Ayachit, *The ParaView guide. A parallel visualization application*. Clifton Park, New York, USA: Kitware, Inc, 2015. ISBN 978-1-930934-30-6
- [18] A. Devresse, N. Cornu, L. Grosheintz-Laval, O. Awile, T. de Geus, F. Pereira, M. Wolf, and H. Contributors, “High-Five - header-only C++ HDF5 interface,” Dec. 2024. doi:[10.5281/zenodo.14272664](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14272664)
- [19] ThinkParQ, Fraunhofer Society, and ITWM, “BeeGFS,” <https://www.beegfs.io>.

- [20] A. Mathur, M. Cao, S. Bhattacharya, A. Dilger, A. Tomas, and L. Vivier, "The new ext4 filesystem: current status and future plans," in *Proceedings of the Linux Symposium*, vol. 2, 2007, pp. 21–34. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kernel.org/doc/ols/2007/ols2007v2-pages-21-34.pdf>